

NOTE ON THE DIOPHANTINE EQUATION $2x^2 - 3y^2 = p$

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The solving of the Diophantine equation

$$2x^2 - 3y^2 = 5 \quad (1)$$

i.e.,

$$2x^2 - 3y^2 - 5 = 0$$

was put as an open Problem 78 by F. Smarandache in [1]. Below this problem is solved completely. Also, we consider here the Diophantine equation

$$l^2 - 6m^2 = -5, \quad (2)$$

i.e.,

$$l^2 - 6m^2 + 5 = 0$$

and the Pellian equation

$$u^2 - 6v^2 = 1, \quad (3)$$

i.e.,

$$u^2 - 6v^2 - 1 = 0.$$

Here we use variables x and y only for equation (1) and l, m for equation (2). We will need the following denotations and definitions:

$$\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\};$$

if

$$F(t, w) = 0$$

is an Diophantine equation, then:

- (a₁) we use the denotation $\langle t, w \rangle$ if and only if (or briefly: iff) t and w are integers which satisfy this equation.
- (a₂) we use the denotation $\langle t, w \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$ iff t and w are positive integers;
 $K(t, w)$ denotes the set of all $\langle t, w \rangle$;
 $K^o(t, w)$ denotes the set of all $\langle t, w \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$;
 $K'(t, w) = K^o(t, w) - \langle 2, 1 \rangle$.

LEMMA 1: If $\langle t, w \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$ and $\langle x, y \rangle \neq \langle 2, 1 \rangle$, then there exists $\langle l, m \rangle$, such that $\langle l, m \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$ and the equalities

$$x = l + 3m \text{ and } y = l + 2m \quad (4)$$

hold.

LEMMA 2: Let $\langle l, m \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$. If x and y are given by (1), then x and y satisfy (4) and $\langle x, y \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$.

We shall note that lemmas 1 and 2 show that the map $\varphi : K^0(l, m) \rightarrow K'(x, y)$ given by (4) is a bijection.

Proof of Lemma 1: Let $\langle x, y \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$ be chosen arbitrarily, but $\langle x, y \rangle \neq \langle 2, 1 \rangle$. Then $y \geq 2$ and $x > y$. Therefore,

$$x = y + m \quad (5)$$

and m is a positive integer. Subtracting (5) into (1), we obtain

$$y^2 - 4my + 5 - 2m^2 = 0. \quad (6)$$

Hence

$$y = y_{1,2} = 2m \pm \sqrt{6m^2 - 5}. \quad (7)$$

For $m = 1$ (7) yields only

$$y = y_1 = 3.$$

indeed

$$1 = y = y_2 < 2$$

contradicts to $y \geq 2$.

Let $m > 1$. Then

$$2m - \sqrt{6m^2 - 5} < 0.$$

Therefore $y = y_2$ is impossible again. Thus we always have

$$y = y_1 = 2m + \sqrt{6m^2 - 5}. \quad (8)$$

Hence

$$y - 2m = \sqrt{6m^2 - 5}. \quad (9)$$

The left-hand side of (9) is a positive integer. Therefore, there exists a positive integer l such that

$$6m^2 - 5 = l^2.$$

Hence l and m satisfy (2) and $\langle l, m \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$.

The equalities (4) hold because of (5) and (8). $\diamond$

Proof of Lemma 2: Let $\langle l, m \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$. Then we check the equality

$$2(l + 3m)^2 - 3(l + 2m)^2 = 5,$$

under the assumption of validity of (2) and the lemma is proved. $\diamond$

Theorem 108 a, Theorem 109 and Theorem 110 from [2] imply the following

THEOREM 1: There exist sets $K_i(l, m)$ such that

$$K_i(l, m) \subset K(l, m) \quad (i = 1, 2),$$

$$K_1(l, m) \cap K_2(l, m) = \emptyset,$$

and $K(l, m)$ admits the representation

$$K(l, m) = K_1(l, m) \cup K_2(l, m).$$

The fundamental solution of $K_1(l, m)$ is $\langle -1, 1 \rangle$ and the fundamental solution of $K_2(l, m)$ is $\langle 1, 1 \rangle$.

Moreover, if $\langle u, v \rangle$ runs $K(u, v)$, then:

(b₁) $\langle l, m \rangle$ runs $K_1(l, m)$ iff the equality

$$l + m\sqrt{6} = (-1 + \sqrt{6})(u + v\sqrt{6}) \quad (10)$$

holds;

(b₂) $\langle l, m \rangle$ runs $K_2(l, m)$ iff the equality

$$l + m\sqrt{6} = (1 + \sqrt{6})(u + v\sqrt{6}) \quad (11)$$

holds.

We must note that the fundamental solution of (3) is $\langle 5, 2 \rangle$. Let u_n and v_n be given by

$$u_n + v_n\sqrt{6} = (5 + 2\sqrt{6})^n \quad (n \in \mathcal{N}). \quad (12)$$

Then u_n and v_n satisfy (11) and $\langle u_n, v_n \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$. Moreover, if n runs $\mathcal{N}$, then $\langle u_n, v_n \rangle$ runs $K^\circ(u, v)$.

Let the sets $K_i^\circ(l, m)$ ($i = 1, 2$) are introduced by

$$K_i^\circ(l, m) = K_i(l, m) \cap \mathcal{N}^2. \quad (13)$$

As a corollary from the above remark and Theorem 1 we obtain

THEOREM 2: The set $K^\circ(l, m)$ may be represented as

$$K^\circ(l, m) = K_1^\circ(l, m) \cup K_2^\circ(l, m), \quad (14)$$

where

$$K_1^\circ(l, m) \cap K_2^\circ(l, m) = \emptyset. \quad (15)$$

Moreover:

(c₁) If n runs $\mathcal{N}$ and the integers l_n and m_n are defined by

$$l_n + m_n\sqrt{6} = (-1 + \sqrt{6})(5 + 2\sqrt{6})^n, \quad (16)$$

then l_n and m_n satisfy (2) and $\langle l_n, m_n \rangle$ runs $K_1^\circ(l, m)$;

(c₂) If n runs $\mathcal{N} \cup \{0\}$ and the integers l_n and m_n are defined by

$$l_n + m_n\sqrt{6} = (1 + \sqrt{6})(5 + 2\sqrt{6})^n, \quad (17)$$

then l_n and m_n satisfy (2) and $\langle l_n, m_n \rangle$ runs $K_2^\circ(l, m)$.

Let φ be the above mentioned bijection. The sets $K_i^{\prime\prime\prime}(x, y)$ ($i = 1, 2$) are introduced by

$$K_i^{\prime\prime\prime}(x, y) = \varphi(K_i^{\circ}(l, m)). \quad (18)$$

From Theorem 2, and especially from (14), (15), and (18) we obtain

THEOREM 3: The set $K^{\prime\prime\prime}(x, y)$ may have the representation

$$K^{\prime\prime\prime}(x, y) = K_1^{\circ}(x, y) \cup K_2^{\circ}(x, y), \quad (19)$$

where

$$K_1^{\circ}(x, y) \cap K_2^{\circ}(x, y) = \emptyset. \quad (20)$$

Moreover:

(d₁) If n runs $\mathcal{N}$ and the integers x_n and y_n are defined by

$$x_n = l_n + 3m_n \text{ and } y_n = l_n + 2m_n, \quad (21)$$

where l_n and m_n are introduced by (16), then x_n and y_n satisfy (1) and $\langle x_n, y_n \rangle$ runs $K_1^{\circ}(x, y)$;

(d₂) If n runs $\mathcal{N} \cup \{0\}$ and the integers x_n and y_n are defined again by (21), but l_n and m_n now are introduced by (17), then x_n and y_n satisfy (1) and $\langle x_n, y_n \rangle$ runs $K_2^{\circ}(x, y)$.

Theorem 3 completely solves F. Smarandache's Problem 78 from [1], because l_n and m_n could be expressed in explicit form using (16) or (17) as well.

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Below we shall introduce a generalization of Smarandache's problem 87 from [1].
If we have to consider the Diophantine equation

$$2x^2 - 3y^2 = p, \quad (22)$$

where $p \neq 2$ is a prime number, then using [2, Ch. VII, exercise 2] and the same method as in the case of (1), we obtain the following result.

THEOREM 4: (1) The necessary and sufficient condition for the solvability of (22) is:

$$p \equiv 5(\text{mod}24) \text{ or } p \equiv 23(\text{mod}24) \quad (23);$$

(2) If (23) is valid, then there exists exactly one solution $\langle x, y \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$ of (22) such that the inequalities $x < \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \cdot p}$; $y < \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot p}$ hold. Every other solution $\langle x, y \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$ of (22) has the form:

$$x = l + 3m$$

$$y = l + 2m,$$

where $\langle l, m \rangle \in \mathcal{N}^2$ is a solution of the Diophantine equation

$$l^2 - 6m^2 = -p.$$

The question how to solve the Diophantine equation, a special case of which is the above one, is considered in Theorem 110 from [2].

REFERENCES:

- [1] F. Smarandache, Proposed Problems of Mathematics. Vol. 2, U.S.M., Chişinău, 1997.
- [2] T. Nagell, Introduction to Number Theory. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1950.

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